

The Philippines' Agrarian Reform: An Unfinished Business?

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Abstract. The Philippines' agrarian reform can be divided into first and second generations. The programs of the first generation are limited to the regulation of tenancy arrangements and land reforms in response to rural unrest rather than achieving rural economic or social objectives. The second generation's objective is to go beyond limited land distribution. With the implementation of the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program (CARP), the coverage of land for acquisition and distribution included all types of farmlands and all kinds of crops. The beneficiaries of CARP received not only support services but also legal services involving agrarian conflicts. This explains why the second generation is a period of agrarian reform, wherein policy objectives and scope of reform are quite comprehensive. Such a change in terms of policy paths proves Torfing's (2009) path dependence argument, saying that these paths are not static. Instead, they are bound to change eventually. Although the second generation may be comprehensive it is not holistic in the sense that the government failed to provide complementary reinforcing mechanisms. Since the government is still settling land distribution, it is unable to make bigger improvements in support services, rural infrastructures, agricultural technologies, agricultural markets, etc. Thus, institutional limits and constraints are not only a hindrance to bringing about significant changes in policies, as argued by Torfing (2009). Instead, the findings show that these constraints, such as the changing priorities of the different administrations, continued resistance from landowners, and lack of political will, have limited the outcomes and impacts of the country's agrarian reform efforts.

Keywords: agrarian reform, first and second generations, path dependence

Introduction

Agricultural land, as a percentage of the Philippines' total land area, was reported at 42.54% (or 12.8 million hectares). The government, in order to promote social justice and industrialization, has implemented through the years land reform programs aimed at acquiring and redistributing farmlands to farmers. With the substantial increase in the number of farms (from 2.17 million in 1960 to 7.43 million in 2022 (see Figure 1), farm sizes have significantly decreased (See Figure 2).

Figure 1
Total Number of Farms: Philippines (1960-2022)

Note. Data on total number of terms are tabulated by residence of operator/location office.
Source. Philippine Statistics Authority, 2012 and 2022 Census of Agriculture and Fisheries.

Based on the 2022 Census of Agriculture and Fisheries Agricultural Farm and Parcel Characteristics released by the Philippines Statistics Authority (PSA), roughly 55.8% (4,146 thousand farms) had size of less than 0.5 hectare; 25% (1,860 thousand farms) had a size between 1.00 to 2.99 hectares; 12.5% (928 thousand farms) had a farm size between 0.5 – 0.99 hectare; and 5.3% (396 thousand farms) had farm sizes of between 3.0 to 6.99 hectares. Only 1.1% (100 thousand) of farms were categorized as large farms with sizes of seven or more hectares. Overall, 93.3% of the 7.4 million farms in the Philippines are less than three hectares in size.

Figure 2
Average Area of Farms: Philippines (1960-2022)

Note. Data on total number of terms are tabulated by residence of operator/location office.
Source. Philippine Statistics Authority, 2012 and 2022 Census of Agriculture and Fisheries.

Figure 3
Percent Distribution of Farms by Size of Farm (2022)

Note. Data on total number of terms are tabulated by residence of operator/location office.

Source. Philippine Statistics Authority, 2012 and 2022 Census of Agriculture and Fisheries.

Agrarian reform in the Philippines is still an unfinished business for two reasons. First, because several lands are available for acquisition and distribution. Quizon (2019) noted that over 65,000 landholdings covering 621,000 hectares are needed to be acquired and distributed. This is also confirmed in the study of Quizon et al. (2023) wherein more than 600,000 hectares of private agricultural lands are still undistributed. Additionally, many private landholdings should have been covered for acquisition and distribution but were left out (Quizon, 2019). The table below shows the summary of agricultural lands distributed by the Department of Agrarian Reform (DAR) and the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR).

Table 1
Summary of Agricultural Lands Distributed by DAR and DENR

	DAR LAD	DENR Patent	Total
Scope (has)	5,423,541	2,514,581	7,938,122
Accomplishment (has)	4,823,037	2,490,218	7,313,255
Percent to scope	88.90%	99%	92%
Agrarian reform beneficiaries	2,807,108	2,344,625	5,151,733
LBP Compo	1,871,645	0	1,871,645
Non-Comp	2,951,896	2,490,218	5,442,114

Source. Land Bank of the Philippines (LBP) compensable lands are covered by various land acquisition and distribution (LAD) models (e.g., operation land transfer, government financial institutions, voluntary offer to sell, and compulsory acquisition).

Thus, the full completion of the *Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program* (CARP) may require new legislation to challenge RA 9700, which scheduled the completion of land acquisition activities for June 20, 2014 (Quizon, 2019). Second, many agrarian reform beneficiaries (ARBs) are still unable to enjoy the right to

security of tenure. Despite the gains of CARP, many of the ARBs' farm productivity and income have not been enough to bring them out of poverty (Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018; Quizon, 2019).

After decades of implementing agrarian reform in the country, it is worth examining the institutional limits and constraints encountered in these periods that hindered the achievement of the desired outcomes and impacts. Given this, the study proposed to examine the historical evolution of agrarian reform policies, programs, and institutions from the Commonwealth period until the Duterte administration.

Conceptual Framework

In the study *Rethinking Path Dependence in Public Research*, Jacob Torfing (2009) explained that there is a need to redefine the explanandum of path dependence arguments in terms of the limits of institutional reform. Meaning, the focus of path dependence arguments in public policy should be on determining the role of institutional limits and constraints in bringing about substantial changes in policies.

In using path dependence in public policy, Torfing (2009) identified some important considerations. First, the path dependence arguments need to focus on how institutional limits and constraints affect bringing about substantial changes in policies. Torfing added that the "window of opportunity" (2009, p.76) will open assuming that there are several social and political actors who agree that the existing policy path is not working and that there is an urgent need for reform.

Second, policy paths are bound to undergo gradual and incremental changes. Policy paths are defined as "a structured coherence of practices governed by rules, norms, cognitions, and images that define what should be regulated, when, how, why, and by whom" (Torfing, 2009, p. 76). This means that policy paths are not homogenous and static. Instead, they are bound to change in the long run.

Third, so long as the path is not altered by new events, social and political actors will continue to support efforts to maintain it. Also, there may be actors who were not involved in the formulation and implementation of the policy but may end up supporting its maintenance. This is because these actors benefit from the existing path. Thus, they can be called sympathetic constituencies (Torfing, 2009).

Lastly, the tendency to resist change, or what is known as institutional inertia, is not only because actors act based on the cost and benefits of certain policies but also because of the sedimentation of rules, norms, and values that define who gets to participate in the deliberation of policy reform. This is crucial precisely because the gradual sedimentation of these factors makes it difficult to deviate from the existing policy path. It is important to note that there is a clear danger in equating path dependence with the impact of institutions. To establish the case of path dependence, it is not enough to show how institutions affect social and political actors. Instead, there is a need to show how social and political actors' reproductive choices contribute to the gradual sedimentation of rules, norms, and values (Torfing, 2009).

From this, one can infer that Torfing's (2009) path dependence shows that policy paths are not static and homogeneous. However, the presence of institutional limits and constraints explains why it is quite difficult to make substantial changes in policies. The study complements the efforts of some scholars, such as You (2015), who have argued that there is a strong tendency toward path dependence in Philippine agrarian reform.

Research and Design Methodology

Research Design

The study used a qualitative method, specifically key informant interviews and primary and secondary documents to examine the historical evolution of agrarian reform policies, programs, and institutions from the Commonwealth era until the Duterte administration.

Data collection

The study used primary and secondary documents and key informant interviews. These documents are statutes or laws, executive orders, administrative orders, department circulars, newspaper clippings, and other primary documents.

Table 2
List of Analyzed Documents

Title	Timeline	Issuing Agency
Republic Act (RA) No. 4054, or the Philippine Rice Share Tenancy Act	1933	Congress
Commonwealth Act (CA) No. 178, or An Act Amending Sections 7, 15, 23, and 29 of Act No. 4054 entitled "An Act to Promote the Wellbeing of Tenants (Aparceros) in Agricultural Lands Devoted to the Production of Rice and to Regulate the Relations Between Them and the Landlords of Said Lands, and for Other Purposes	1936	Congress
RA No. 34 An Act Amending Certain Sections of RA 4054, as amended	1946	Congress
Executive Order (EO) No. 355 Creating the Land Settlement and Development Corporation and Dissolving the National Land Settlement Administration, and the Rice and Corn Production Administration and the Machinery and Equipment Department of the National Development Company	1950	Executive Branch
RA 1199 Agricultural Tenancy Act of the Philippines	1954	
R.A. 1160 An Act to Further Implement the Free Distribution of Agricultural Lands of the Public Domain as Provided for in Commonwealth Act Numbered Six Hundred and Ninety-one, as Amended, to Abolish the Land Settlement and Development Corporation Created under EO 355 and to Create in its Place the National Resettlement and Rehabilitation Administration, and for Other Purposes	1954	Congress
RA 1400 Land Reform Act of 1955	1955	Congress
RA 3844 Agricultural Land Reform Code	1963	Congress
RA 6389 An Act Amending RA 3844	1971	Congress

Presidential Decree (PD) No. 27 Decreeing the Emancipation of Tenants from the Bondage of the Soil, Transferring to them the Ownership of the Land they till and Providing the Instruments and Mechanism therefore	1972	Executive Branch
General Order No. 1	1972	Executive Branch
Proclamation No. 1081 Proclamation of Martial Law in the Philippines	1972	Executive Branch
EO 129 Reorganization Act of the Agrarian Reform	1987	Executive Branch
EO 129-A Reorganization Act of the Department of Agrarian Reform (DAR)	1987	Executive Branch
EO 229 Providing the Mechanisms for the Implementation of the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program (CARP)	1987	Executive Branch
The 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines	1987	Executive Branch
Proclamation No. 131 Instituting a Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program	1987	Executive Branch
RA 6657 Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Law of 1988	1988	Congress
EO 405 Vesting in the Land Bank of the Philippines the Primary Responsibility to Determine the Land Valuation and Compensation for All Lands Covered under RA 6657	1990	Executive Branch
RA 7881 An Act Amending Certain Provisions of RA 6657	1995	Congress
RA 7905 An Act to Strengthen the Implementation of CARP	1995	Congress
RA 8532 An Act Strengthening Further the CARP by Providing Augmentation Fund therefor, Amending for the Purpose of Section 63 of RA 6657	1998	Congress
DAR AO 9 of 1998 (Rules and Regulations on the Acquisition, Valuation, Compensation, and Distribution of Deferred Commercial Farms)	1988	DAR
EO 151 Establishing the Farmers Trust Development Program and Providing Institutional Reforms and Fund Mechanisms for Mobilizing Long Term Private Sector Capital for Rural Development	1999	Executive Branch
DAR AO 2 of 1999 (Rules and Regulations Governing Joint Economic Enterprises in Agrarian Reform Areas)	1999	DAR
DAR AO 9 of 2006 (Revised Rules and Regulations Governing Agribusiness Venture Arrangements in Agrarian Reform Areas)	2006	DAR
DAR AO 2 of 2008 (Guidelines Governing Lease of Lands under Agribusiness Venture Arrangements in Agrarian Reform Areas and the Determination of Lease Rental)	2008	DAR

RA 9700 An Act Strengthening the CARP, Extending the Acquisition and Distribution of All Agricultural Lands, Instituting Necessary Reforms, Amending for the Purpose Certain Provisions of Republic Act No. 6657	2009	Congress
Mindanao 2020 Peace and Development Framework Plan 2011-2030	2011	MDA
Ambisyon Natin 2040	2016	NEDA
The Philippine Development Plan (PDP) 2017-2022	2017	NEDA
EO 75 Directing All Departments, Bureaus, Offices, and Instrumentalities of the Government to Identify Lands Owned by the Government Devoted to or Suitable for Agriculture for Distribution to Qualified Beneficiaries	2019	Executive Branch
Philippine Development Plan (2023-2028)	2022	NEDA

Table 3 shows the profile of each informant in the study. Key informants were experts and lawyers in agrarian reform and government officials from DAR national and regional offices. Below is the list of key informants.

Table 3
Profile of Key Informants

Code	Position	Organization	Interview Date
KII_001	Research and Advocacy Advisor; former NGO Legal Officer	Non-Government Organization (NGO)	February 13, 2023
KII_002	Consultant	NGO	February 14, 2023
KII_003	University Research Associate	University of the Philippines, Los Baños	February 27, 2023
KII_004	University Researcher V	University of the Philippines, Los Baños	March 10, 2023
KII_005	Policy and Planning Service, Planning Officer V	DAR National Office	March 13, 2023
KII_006	Provincial Agrarian Reform Program Officer II	DAR National Office	March 13, 2023
KII_007	Executive Director	NGO	March 17, 2023
KII_008	Municipal Agrarian Reform Officer	DAR Regional	March 21, 2023
KII_009	Bureau of Land Tenure and Improvement	DAR National Office	May 26, 2023
KII_010	Private lawyer	Private Law Office	July 6, 2023
KII_011	Former AVA point person; Special Agrarian Reform Officer	DAR Regional	July 24, 2023
KII_012	Municipal Agrarian Reform Officer	DAR Regional	July 26, 2023

Data Analysis

For the data analysis, a coding sheet was created for the documents and key informant interviews to answer the historical evolution of agrarian reform policies, programs, and institutions. The coding sheet started with the assignment of codes, with separate matrices for documents and key informants. Another set of matrices was used to identify the main themes and subthemes for the documents and key informants. Thematic analysis was used for this research.

Results and Discussion

The study employed Torfing's (2009) path dependence as the theoretical lens for analyzing the first and second generations of the Philippine agrarian reform. It used thematic analysis in analyzing the KII results to generate new insights on the historical evolution of agrarian reform policies, institutions, and programs.

First Generation

The programs of the first generation are limited to the regulation of tenancy arrangements and land reform in response to the growing peasant rebellion in Central Luzon. It was only in the President Diosdado Macapagal administration when policy provisions in RA 3844 of 1963 (e.g., diverting landlord capital towards industrial development, and establishing family-size farms) to industrialize the agriculture sector. These provisions would also appear in President Ferdinand Marcos Sr.'s RA 6389 of 1971. One can also notice that these efforts are limited to regulating small-scale farmers, despite the presence of multinational corporations and agro-industrial enterprises.

Regulation of Tenancy Arrangements

There was the inadequacy of subsistence farming as a sustainable way of life for the country and thus the need to promote productivity in agriculture. However, the earlier land reform efforts were not aimed at improving the socio-economic conditions of farmers and tenants. Instead, they were focused on pacifying rural unrest (KII_005, personal communication, March 13, 2023). Figure 4 shows the regulation of tenancy arrangements during the administrations of President Manuel Quezon, President Manuel Roxas, and President Elpidio Quirino, while Figure 5 illustrates the institutional limits and constraints encountered in these periods that hindered the achievement of the desired outcomes and impact.

Manuel L. Quezon. Before the election of Quezon, Camba (2019) explained an interesting point about the food regime in the late colonial Philippines from 1901 to 1941. During this period, the US agribusiness and Philippine elites appropriated unpaid work from the agrarian classes of labor to the production of the country's rice, coconut, and sugar. Specifically, Camba (2019) highlighted the importance of draft animals to the lives of the agrarian classes. These draft animals were used to plow the soil and graze the land without any additional cost. While capitalists paid the agrarian classes at fixed rates, they did not pay the agrarian classes for the use of their draft animals. Nevertheless, such a system produced huge quantities of coconut and sugar products that were exported to the American consumer market. These products were sold at cheaper prices and consequently contributed to the profitability

of US agribusiness (Camba, 2019). From this, one can infer how draft animals were a key feature of unpaid work in the food regime in the late colonial Philippines.

Figure 4
Regulation of Tenancy Arrangements (Policy Path)

Policy Themes	Manuel L. Quezon (1935-1944)	Manuel Roxas (1942-1948)	Elpidio Quirino (1948-1953)
Agrarian reform policy objective	Tool to pacify unrest	●	●
Tenant and landlord arrangements	50/50 sharing arrangement	● 70/30 sharing arrangement	●
Attempts to regulate land ownership	Landed elite came into the picture	●	●
Land acquisition and distribution (LAD)	The newly-established National Settlement Administration (NLSA) paved the way for resettlement projects in Cotabato and Isabela	●	▲ Functions of NLSA was transferred to LASEDECO, LASEDECO was facilitated the acquisition, settlement, and cultivation of agricultural lands. Tenants had the right to settle for 25 years.
Coverage of land	Rice Land	●	●
Government reorganization & coordination	Establishment of National Land Settlement Administration (NLSA)	●	▲ Establishment of the Land Settlement Administration Development Corporation (LASEDECO) thus, dissolving NLSA
Financial support mechanism			▲ Opened Financial Support and Credit Initiatives
Support services		▲ Agreement-Based Expense Sharing for Construction and Maintenance	▲ Opened skills training Opportunities, Promoted Mechanized Agriculture, Developed Agricultural Infrastructure, Provided Education Support
Legal assistance and conflict resolution		▲ Resolution of Disagreements and Cost Liability	●
Monitoring, evaluation accountability checks			
Manner of rental payment		▲ Distribution of Crop-Based on Resource Contributions of tenant and landlord	●
Tenant's/ARB's rights			

Legend ● Continuation ▲ Change ⊘ Discontinuation

Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents)

To regulate the relationships between the landowners and tenants, Quezon started his agrarian policy initiatives in the 1930s. He was sensitive to the peasant unrest in Central Luzon and wanted to meet its demands without discomfoting his landlord friends and allies (Wurfel, 1983). In this case, land reform was used to pacify rural unrest. Even after the Philippines gained its independence from American colonial rule, the former colonizers had a major influence on the country. The Americans specifically influenced the change in the country's tenurial status (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). In general, many reform laws

focused on land settlement and tenancy projects to quell rural unrest rather than advance economic or social objectives (Elvinia, 2011).

One of the major reforms in Quezon was RA 4054, also known as the Rice Share Tenancy Act (the first tenancy reform). RA 4054 regulated the relations between the tenants of rice and the landowners (RA 4054, 1933; Putzel, 1992; Elvinia, 2011). It contained provisions for a 50/50 sharing arrangement between the tenant and the landowner, a 10% cap on interest rates for tenant loans, and a ban on evicting tenants without tenuous grounds (RA 4054, 1933; Elvinia, 2011; Galang, 2020). During this time, the National Land Settlement Administration (NLSA) was established, paving the way for resettlement projects in the Koronadal Valley, the Allah Valley in Cotabato, and the Mallig Plains in Isabela. However, it had resettled only 8,300 families with a cost of PHP11 million (Putzel, 1992).

There were implementation issues and a string of farm rebellions unrelated to agrarian laws. In 1930, there was widespread peasant unrest under the Commonwealth due to securing access to land. Putzel (1992) noted the strong peasant uprisings in Central Luzon, where there was a widespread tenancy on the large, landed estates. The peasant groups who led these uprisings were: the Partido Komunista ng Pilipinas (PKP), or the Communist Party of the Philippines, and the Socialist Party. Both groups claimed to have 100,000 members. In addition, there was a lack of confidence in the government (Fifield, 1951). Pedro Abad Santos, the socialist leader in central Luzon, did not believe in Quezon's land reform efforts. Santos claimed that the peasants should continue to fight because "no capitalist government could give them what they deserve" (Fifield, 1951, p.14). Thus, there was a failure to regulate landlord-tenant relations (Lanzona, 2019). When tenants demanded a 50-50 sharing arrangement, landlords threatened them with dismissal (Fifield, 1951). From this, one can infer that the rise of communist movements was due to social injustice and the government's failure to address land distribution issues (KII_002, personal communication, February 14, 2023).

Aside from the existence of a revolutionary government, the Japanese occupation of the country contributed to the limited impact of Quezon's overall efforts (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). Velasco (1990) explained that the Japanese occupation lasted from 1942 to 1945.

In connection with this, there were political and dramatic drivers of land reform instead of well-being and agri-productivity. This meant a lack of genuine political will to improve the lives of the farmers (KII_010, personal communication, July 6, 2023). In response, a UPLB researcher (KII_004) confirmed the lack of political will of the Quezon administration to implement its law on sharing arrangements. Thus, she pointed out that politics is a deterrent to land reform efforts.

There was also the presence of the economic and political power of the elite in the early land reform. Rich people could not be brought to justice because of their economic and political power. Rich landlords, who owned huge tracts of land, were also politicians. The respondent described it as the symbiotic and mutual power dynamics of land ownership and political influence. By being rich landlords and politicians at the same time, their economic and political power helped them to keep their land and protect their property (KII_002, personal communication, February 14, 2023). This was a stark difference from other neighboring countries (e.g. Japan and Taiwan), which were able to eliminate the elite class (Kawagoe, 1999; Miller, 2013).

In the end, the Quezon administration was unable to acquire or distribute enough land to peasants. Instead, “the Commonwealth period saw an acceleration of land concentration” (Putzel, 1992, p.59) among corporate landholders and landlords.

Figure 5
Regulation of Tenancy Arrangements (Institutional Limits and Constraints)

Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents)

Manuel Roxas. Like Quezon, Roxas was linked to the landed elites of Central Luzon (Wurfel, 1983). The country's natural resources and land also remained under US control and ownership (Lanzona, 2019). The rebellion against the Philippine government was still a major concern. For instance, the *Hukbalahap* (Hukbo ng Bayan Laban sa Hapon- People's Anti-Japanese Army) was formed in the tenant-dominated region of Central Luzon in March 1942. By the end of the of the Japanese occupation, the Huks, as they came to be known, worked together with PKP and had freed significant areas in Central Luzon from landlord rule. Their peasant experience

and the fight against the Japanese led to a new sense of aspiration—that was, the demand for agrarian reform after the war (Putzel, 1992). In November 1948, the *Hukbalahap* renamed itself as the *Hukbong Mapagpalaya ng Bayan* (HMB, People's Liberation Army) of the PKP (Greenberg, 1995).

In this case, the Huks capitalized on two kinds of social unrest in the country to expand their membership. The first one dealt with the rise in massive armaments and lawlessness in the country because of the Japanese occupation. The second stemmed from the struggle of peasants in Central Luzon (Fifield, 1951). Given the relationship of Roxas with the landed elites, the Huks viewed Roxas as the candidate of the landowners and big business interests, who were interested in maintaining a close economic connection with the US, while urging the country's political independence (Fifield, 1951). From this, one can infer that the presence of the landed elites, US influence over natural and land resources, and the HUK movement continued during the Manuel Roxas administration.

Roxas, in response, used land reform as a tool to attract peasants away from the Huks (Fifield, 1951). Land reform was used in response to the insurgency. There were two major reforms implemented to improve the sharing arrangement and provide safeguards for the ejection of tenants (KII_005, personal communication, March 13, 2023). First, RA 34 established the 70-30 sharing arrangements and regulated share-tenancy contracts (RA 34, 1963; Galang, 2020). Only 30% of the rice crop should be given to the landlord, and 70% should be kept by the tenant, provided that the latter gives the farm equipment and work animals as well as financing for the planting and harvesting. Second, RA 55 provided safeguards for the ejection of tenants. This was implemented in case tenants were not able to immediately provide their required share to their landowners (RA 55, 1946).

Like the Quezon administration, there was a lack of confidence in the Roxas government. Luis Taruc, the Huk chief, shared a similar lack of confidence in the Roxas administration. There were also reports wherein landlords threatened tenants with dismissal, specifically those demanding the 70-30 sharing arrangement (Fifield, 1951). Tenants could not do anything because of the economic and political power of the elites during the early land reform efforts (KII_002, personal communication, February 14, 2023).

Elpidio Quirino. The US continued to influence the country's land reform efforts during the time of Elpidio Quirino. The 1952 Hardie Report (named after Robert S. Hardie) recommended the abolition of share tenancy (Lanzona, 2019) and the redistribution of land to 70% of the tenants in the country (You, 2015). All these land reform efforts were done in response to the Huk situation (You, 2015; Lanzona, 2019).

Nevertheless, Elpidio Quirino had different land reform priorities during his time. Quirino implemented Executive Order (EO) 355, which created the Land Settlement and Development Corporation (LASEDECO). This was considered his biggest contribution to land reform. In this case, the EO abolished the NLSA, which was created in Quezon's time, and transferred its duties to LASEDECO. Specifically, LASEDECO facilitated the acquisition, settlement, and cultivation of agricultural lands to afford opportunity to landless tenants and farmers. The government identified LASEDECO areas in rural areas. Those who cultivated the identified areas

were given the right to stay there. It should be noted that only the right to stay in the area was given to them. They did not receive the land that they cultivated. They were given the right to settle for 25 years. At the same time, the Quirino administration continued the 70-30 sharing arrangement (EO 355, 1950).

Like Quezon and Roxas' experiences, the Huk movement was considered a constraint in the land reform efforts of Quirino. A DAR national official (KII_005) confirmed the insurgency movements during this time. In addition to this, there was a lack of confidence among the members of these movements in the Quirino government precisely because the 70-30 sharing arrangement had not been properly implemented (Fifield, 1951). In examining this, one can observe that the Huk movement tirelessly fights the administrations of Quezon, Roxas, and Quirino in pushing for land equality.

Another institutional constraint was the changing priorities of the different administrations, which led to the failure of the country's land reform (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). While Quirino continued to implement the 70-30 sharing arrangement, he gave more attention to LASEDECO projects.

Land Reform

In the regulation of tenancy arrangements, the administrations of Ramon Magsaysay, Diosdado Macapagal, and Ferdinand Marcos Sr. pushed for land reform programs. When the Huks collapsed during the time of Magsaysay, the succeeding administration's land reform policy intent was the advancement of the well-being of small farmers and agricultural productivity. The covered lands for reform were rice and corn lands. Figure 6 shows the land reform initiatives from the administrations of Magsaysay to Marcos Sr., while Figure 7 illustrates the institutional limits and constraints encountered in these periods that hindered the achievement of the desired outcomes and impacts.

Ramon Magsaysay. In 1953, Magsaysay ran for president and won based on the platform of land reform (You, 2015; Portera & Hila, 2020). Magsaysay gained the trust of the peasantry when he was appointed Secretary of National Defense. The military feared and respected Magsaysay at the same time. This image gave hope to the peasants that someone in the government was serious about improving their conditions (Portera & Hila, 2020). Additionally, Magsaysay's military reforms and increased pressure on the rebels, resulted in the collapse of the HMB movement (You, 2015; Portera & Hila, 2020).

Edward Lansdale, who was Magsaysay's right hand when he was the Secretary of Defense, supported his reform efforts. Lansdale argued that the problem with the Huks was not about the lack of land. Instead, the problem was about the Quirino government's ruling style and the presence of oligarchy, which Washington had used to control the country. Thus, Lansdale suggested the community development approach in dealing with the Huks. Following the advice of Lansdale, Magsaysay created the Presidential Assistant on Community Development (PACD), putting community development at the core of its development projects. The main objective of the PACD programs was political decentralization with a clear understanding that the barrio council would not challenge imperial Manila. Such kind of development strategy gained many supporters in the Philippines who believed in the importance of the community (Immerwahr, 2015).

On that note, Portera and Hila (2020) pointed out that the Magsaysay administration used land reform as a strategy to improve the conditions of the peasantry to prevent the rise of serious peasant unrest. The authors argued that there was a sincere effort to alleviate the plight of landless peasants and enhance the economic position of tenant farmers. In response, a UPLB researcher (KII_004) confirmed Magsaysay's pro-poor policies to help the poor.

Magsaysay implemented three major land reforms. First, the Agricultural Tenancy Act of 1954 (RA 1199) established the classification of agricultural tenancy: share tenancy and leasehold tenancy. Share tenancy involves joint agricultural production where one party contributes labor while the other party contributes land and production items. Produce was shared based on contributions. On the other hand, in leasehold tenancy, a person undertakes to cultivate the land and pays the landowner either a percentage of the production, a fixed amount in money, or both, depending on the agreement. Nevertheless, both classifications of agricultural tenancy should lead to the transformation of tenants into leaseholders.

Second, the Land Reform Act of 1955 (RA 1400) provided for the expropriation of large estates and their distribution to tenants. The scope of expropriation and distribution was public agricultural lands and private agricultural lands, specifically where agrarian conflicts existed. In terms of crop coverage, land reform expanded to cover not only tenanted rice lands but also corn lands. This law also imposed retention limits of 300 hectares for individuals (RA 1400, 1955). The Land Reform Act of 1955 was the first law to set retention limits on ownership of agricultural lands.

Third, RA 1160 of 1954 aimed at providing home lots and farmlands in Palawan and Mindanao to rebel returnees. These resettlement projects in Mindanao started during the time of Magsaysay (KII_011, personal communication, July 24, 2023). Small farmers and tenants used to borrow loans with high interest rates from their landowners. The government gave loans to small farmers and tenants with low interest rates (six to eight percent) to help break that bond between tenants and landowners. RA 1160 of 1954 also abolished LASEDECO and established the National Resettlement and Rehabilitation Administration (NARRA) to resettle dissidents and landless farmers (RA 1160, 1954).

Despite Magsaysay's efforts to alleviate the plight of landless peasants, institutional constraints hindered his land reform efforts. One of these was a change in land reform priorities (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). Quezon and Roxas focused on the regulation of tenancy arrangements. However, during the time of Magsaysay, his land reform was focused more on the resettlement of dissidents.

In connection with this, there was a discontinuity in the land reform program during this period. The discontinuity of some programs was a reason why there was little success in land reform efforts (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). For example, it was during Magsaysay's time that he abolished LASEDECO and replaced it with NARRA, which focused on the resettlement of dissidents and landless farmers.

Figure 6
Land Reform (Policy Path)

Policy Themes	Ramon Magsaysay (1963-1967)	Diosdado Macapagal (1961-1965)	Ferdinand Marcos Sr. (1965-1986)
Agrarian reform policy	▲ Alleviate the plight of landless peasants	● Advance the well-being of small farmers and agricultural productivity	●
Tenant and landlord arrangements	▲ Transformation of tenants into leaseholders	▲ Full abolition of share-tenancy system achieve owner-cultivatorship farms	● Establishing owner-cultivatorship farms, economic family-size farms and cooperative-owned farms
Attempts to regulate land ownership	▲ Maximum land retention of 300 hectares of contiguous rice lands per individual landowner	● Maximum land retention of 75-hectares per individual landowner	● Maximum land retention of 24 hectares per individual landowner then reduced to 7 hectares
Land acquisition and distributions (lad)	● Narra's role in redistributing private and/or public land as family-size farms to as many landless citizens including land with agrarian conflicts	● Enhanced land resettlement and public land distribution and establishment of authority for equitable lad of private or public agricultural land	●
Coverage of land	▲ Public rice and corn lands as well as private agricultural lands where agrarian conflict exists	● Public and private rice and corn lands within a 75-hectare retention limit	● "Primarily" public and private rice and corn lands under a system of sharecropping or lease-tenancy
Government reorganization & coordination	▲ Establishment of national resettlement and rehabilitation administration (narra) thus, abolishing (lasedeco)	▲ Transfer of powers and functions to land authority thus, abolishing narra	▲ Establishment of Department of Agrarian Reform
Financial support mechanism	● Provided loan and credit opportunities from the agricultural credit and cooperative financing administration (acefa) as well as incentives for agricultural production by tenant farmers	▲ Establishment and operation of the Land Bank of the Philippines to support the division of land to small landholders and extend diverse loans to small farmers	●
Support services	● Assistance in securing equipment, supplies, and materials for settler	●	●
Legal Assistance and Conflict Resolution	● Interpretation, enforcement and resolution of doubts in favor of the tenant	○	○
Monitoring, Evaluation Accountability Checks	▲ Keeping the president and congress informed about reform progress	○	○
Manner of Rental Payment	▲ Opened flexible options for payment (1) monetary payment, (2) payment in produce and (3) combination of monetary and produce payment	●	● Flexible payment system for land acquisition and distribution
Tenant's/ARB's Rights	▲ Tenant-lessee's rights: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal establishment of tenancy relationship • Just causes for dispossession and termination of contract • Security of tenure • Autonomy in farming methods • Tenant's access to premises of the land 	▲ Establishment of agricultural labor rights and provision on equal application of labor laws to industrial and agricultural sectors	●

Legend ● Continuation ▲ Change ○ Discontinuation

Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents)

Immerwahr (2015) argued that Magsaysay's PACD programs were stopgap measures rather than extensive land redistribution efforts. He pointed out that the PACD programs failed to succeed because some barrio council leaders did not always want projects that PACD proposed. Also, during this time, the Philippine economy stalled in the early 1960s. This explained why inequality grew. Most importantly, Magsaysay died in 1957, leading to a lack of a genuine Filipino leader for the PACD.

In addition, under the Land Reform Act of 1955, the retention limits on ownership of agricultural lands were high. These were “300 hectares of contiguous lands planted to rice, 600 hectares for corporate farms, and 1,024 hectares for private farms other than rice” (Ballesteros et al., 2017, p. 3). Also, Congress provided a small amount of funding to implement the Land Reform Act of 1955 (You, 2015; Lanzona, 2019; Portera and Hila, 2020) and the Agricultural Tenancy Act of 1954 (Lanzona, 2019).

Several representatives in Congress also belonged to the landed political elite, making the passage of the bill (Land Reform Act of 1955) against their interests. By the time Congress passed the law, what was legislated was a watered-down version of the original (Murray, 1972; Portera & Hila, 2020). Such a situation exemplified the symbiotic and mutual power of the dynamics of landownership and political influence (KII_002, personal communication, February 24, 2023). The political and economic power of the landed political elites allowed them to keep their land. Thus, Murray (1972) noted that Magsaysay lacked the political backing necessary for a reasonable land reform policy.

Given these constraints, the Agricultural Tenancy Act of 1954 and the Land Reform Act of 1955 were not implemented effectively. Congress failed to provide the required budget for their implementation (You, 2015; Lanzona, 2019). Nevertheless, Magsaysay was successful in controlling the insurgency (Murray, 1972; Portera & Hila, 2020). When the insurgency stopped, land reform failed to become a priority for Congress (Murray, 1972). In examining this, it is interesting to note that the US lost interest in the country’s land reform efforts when the Huk movement disappeared. Also, the administration failed to address the concentration of land among wealthy families.

Diosdado Macapagal. After Magsaysay, Diosdado Macapagal was quiet about land reform in his first few years in office. In 1963, he made a surprising move to draft RA 3844 of 1963, or the Agricultural Land Reform Code, which aimed to redistribute rice and croplands of 25 hectares and over. At the end of Macapagal’s administration, it became clear that the real objective of his land reform was to win support for his reelection in 1965 and not really to put genuine effort into implementing the Agricultural Land Reform Code of 1963 (You, 2015).

Macapagal’s major land reform, the Agricultural Land Reform Code of 1963, called for the full abolition of the share tenancy system. The law was made up of two stages: 1) to convert share tenants to leaseholders, and 2) to convert leaseholders to owner-cultivators. The main goal was the “ownership-cultivatorship of family-based farms” (Lanzona, 2019, p. 283). In connection with this, the Code aimed to divert landlord capital toward industrial development (RA 3844, Section 2, 1963). From this, one can infer that the policy objective to industrialize the agriculture sector is in place in the Macapagal administration.

While the policy objective to industrialize the agriculture sector was already on paper during this time, a former NGO consultant (KII_002) argued that other Southeast Asian countries had more comprehensive agro-industrial policies as compared to the Philippines. These neighboring countries implemented these policies due to a highly centralized government.

Nevertheless, Macapagal focused more on the implementation of the Code, which involved several institutions. One was the Land Reform Project Administration (LRPA), which oversaw the entire program's implementation, and the other was the National Land Reform Council (NLRC), which was charged with coordinating various agencies for this program. Land Bank of the Philippines (LBP) was tasked with purchasing land estates and aiding tenants (Lanzano, 2019). The Code abolished NARRA and transferred its functions and responsibilities to the Land Authority (RA 3844, 1963).

There were institutional constraints in the implementation of the Code. First, the program had low budgetary support and very weak administrative support (Lanzano, 2019). Second, the scope of the program was limited to rice and corn farms (Balisacan, 2007). While the Code lowered the retention limit of ownership of agricultural land to 75 ha from 300 hectares (Magsaysay period), the program excluded coconut, sugar, and abaca lands (Lanzano, 2019).

In effect, the Code did not materialize. Landlords decided to convert and cultivate the land themselves to avoid this reform. Also, Congress only allocated PHP 1 million for the program, even though the proposed budget was PHP 1.5 billion. Lastly, not a single square meter was appropriated in 1965 because LBP was not yet formally established during this time (Lanzano, 2019).

Ferdinand Marcos, Sr. After Macapagal, Ferdinand Marcos Sr. initiated the actual land distribution to tenants. Marcos Sr. declared martial law and abolished Congress under Proclamation No. 1081 on September 21, 1972. In this case, land reform became an instrument to gather support for the martial law regime (Balisacan, 2007). A UPLB researcher (KII_004) further explained that when Marcos Sr. declared martial law, many people were against it. However, his land reform appeased the masses. This explained how Marcos Sr.'s land reform contributed to his image as pro-mass and pro-poor. Nevertheless, Bello (2019) described him as a predatory ruler and a dictator who used his political power for personal ends. He added that Marcos Sr. was not counterrevolutionary, contrary to what he claimed. This was because Marcos Sr. was not leading a mass insurgency against liberal democracy and there was no revolutionary threat to which he was responding.

One of the major reforms of this administration was Presidential Decree (PD) 27, which implemented Operation Land Transfer (OLT). Under OLT of PD 27, rice and corn lands were to be acquired from landowners and distributed to tenants and lessees. The Marcos Sr. administration engaged in accessible land distribution through OLT and declared that rice and corn tenants were deemed landowners (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). PD 27 was a significant land reform policy because it gave ownership and responsibility to tillers after receiving their lands from the government. Tillers did not anticipate receiving land from private landowners (KII_08, personal communication, March 21, 2023). In this case, beneficiaries under OLT received a certificate of land transfer and an emancipation patent (EP) (KII_009, personal communication, May 26, 2023). These distributed lands were not allowed to be sold or undergo mortgages (KII_010, personal communication, July 6, 2023).

In terms of PD 27 provisions, the landowner's maximum land retention was seven hectares, which was set at 75 hectares during the Macapagal period. The land cost was equivalent to two and one-half times the average harvest of three normal crop years. Share tenants who worked over seven hectares could purchase the land they

tilled, while those who worked less than seven hectares would become leaseholders (PD 27, 1972). During this time, DAR used to compute for land valuation (KII_008, personal communication, March 21, 2023).

Figure 7
Land Reform (Institutional Limits and Constraints)

Institutional Limits and Constraints	Ramon Magsaysay (1963-1967)	Diosdado Macapagal (1961-1965)	Ferdinand Marcos Sr. (1965-1986)
Landlord's exploitation and resistance	● Landlords threatened with dismissal tenants demanding for the 50-50 sharing arrangement	●	●
Foreign and elite rule in economic and political environments	● Magsaysay lacked political backing; members of Congress belonged to the landed political elite	● Congress watered down RA 3844	●
Ingenuine/fluctuating political will	● Political and dramatic interests as deterrents of land reform ● Discontinuity of programs	●	● Agrarian Reform as a mere tool to building a pro-mass and pro-poor image
Clashes with peasant movement	▲ The collapse of the Huks	●	●
Lack of budget and support services	▲ Congress gave small budget for the implementation of RA 1199 and RA 1400	● Low budgetary support	●
Performance issues	● Lack of agro-industrial policies and development	●	●
Land use issues	● Land as a political commodity	●	●
Outcomes and Impacts			
Conceptualization	● Industrial approach to agriculture	●	▲ Transformative intent by breaking free from old feudal relationships.
Tenancy Relations and Land Distribution	● RA 1199 and RA 1400 were not properly implemented	● Tenants were beholden to their landowners	● Challenges in accessing emancipation measures
Welfare of Farmers	▲ Integrated people into the political system by establishing land resettlement programs, particularly in Mindanao	● High rate of share tenancy	▲ Landownership Declarations of rice and corn land farmers
Implementation	▲ Suppressed insurgency by dismantling haciendas	● RA 3844 did not materialize	● Issues on "distribute but not yet paid" (DNYP) and "distribute but not yet documented" (DNYD)

Legend ● Continuation ▲ Change ✕ Discontinuation

Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents)

It should be noted that it was during the Marcos Sr. administration that DAR was created, and an Agrarian Reform Special Account Fund was established to facilitate the actual land distribution for rice and corn lands (RA 6389, 1971; Galang,

2020). DAR was responsible for identifying the needed support services for farmers. Once the support services were given to them, DAR annotated the EPs of the farmers with the support services they received (KII_008, personal communication, March 21, 2023).

There were institutional limits and constraints to land reform efforts during the Marcos Sr. administration. First, under Martial law, there was swift action regarding land reform due to fear of non-compliance, strong presidential authority, and political influence. Thus, the distribution of rice and corn lands was put into effect quickly (KII_009, personal communication, May 26, 2023). Landlords were afraid of not complying, and at the same time, they respected the president's authority.

Second, while there was swift action under Martial law to implement land reform, the design of PD 27 was quite problematic. The law covered only tenanted rice and corn lands, even if Marcos Sr. declared the entire country an agrarian reform area. However, the limited coverage of PD 27 was itself a setback (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023). It exempted haciendas and plantations growing coconuts, sugarcane, and tobacco (Balisacan, 2007; Unyon ng mga Manggagawa sa Agrikultura, 2019). A DAR official agreed that high-value commercial plantations (e.g., coconut, sugar) escaped from the Marcos Sr. Program (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023). In connection with this, PD 27 included tenanted farmers but excluded landless farm workers from being beneficiaries (Balisacan, 2007; Elvinia, 2011). Also, landlords converted their lands to exempted crops, and others were subdivided among relatives under the seven-hectare limit (You, 2015). In short, landlords used crop switching to avoid PD 27 (KII_010, personal communication, July 6, 2023).

Third, there were problems with distributed but not yet documented (DNYD) and distributed but not yet paid (DNYP) lands. On DNYD, some lands had been distributed to the farmers, even though DAR had not completed the needed documentation for submission to LBP for payment. On DNYP, some lands had been distributed to the farmers, but landowners in rice and corn lands did not receive payment for their land. Also, landowners had concerns about the valuation of rice and corn lands. The land valuation at that time was quite low, and consequently, there were landowners who brought their cases to the Court of Appeals and Supreme Court to seek a judicial determination of just compensation (Quizon, 2019).

Fourth, the new rice technologies made farming dependent on foreign-made fertilizers. This was a significant issue because these fertilizers were under the control of multinational corporations, making inputs beyond the reach of most rice-producing peasants (Lanzano, 2019). In connection with this, technocrats managed land transfers; thus, peasants had to go through the time-consuming and difficult procedures necessary for the standard banking system (Lanzano, 2019).

Fifth, there were illegal conversions in resettlement areas. A respondent emphasized that there were illegal and unauthorized conversions happening in resettlement areas during this period (KII_008, personal communication, March 21, 2023). However, Quizon (2019) noted that illegal conversions were not yet rampant at that time because the crop coverage was limited to tenanted rice and corn lands.

In the end, the efforts to implement meaningful land reform did not materialize (Marin et al., 2019). The accomplishment report from the Ministry of Agrarian Reform dated December 31, 1984 showed that the target scope of Marcos' program to transfer

lands through emancipation patents (EPs) was 427, 623 with 716, 520 hectares. However, only 3.3% (or 13, 027) of the targeted beneficiaries received EPs with 17, 586 hectareage (Tadem, 2022). While Marcos Sr.'s land reform accomplishments were low, Borras (2007) acknowledged that his program contributed to the reform efforts in the country because it weakened the political power of landlords of rice and corn farms.

Second Generation

The second generation is a period of agrarian reform. It should be noted that land reform is different from agrarian reform. Lanzona (2019) points out that land reform refers to a narrower distribution of land with a limited group of beneficiaries (e.g., tillers), while agrarian reform has a broader set of objectives in the sense that it alters not only the relationship between landowners and tenants but also its role in overall productivity. In the same way, Jacobs (2010) defines agrarian reform as constituting widespread land redistribution, provision of infrastructure, support services, and a whole program of democratic reforms. Thus, Marcos Sr.'s land program is included in the first generation because of its narrower scope distribution of land (rice and corn farms) with a limited group of beneficiaries.

Agrarian Reform

Key informants from academia, NGOs, and DAR at the regional and national levels, argued that the most significant agrarian reform policy is RA 6657, or CARL. It covered both public and private agricultural lands, regardless of crops. Aside from land distribution, the program aimed to provide support services to ARBs. However, the program encountered institutional limits and constraints (e.g., landed political actors, strong resistance of landowners, lack of urgency of the Corazon Aquino administration to implement CARP, unprepared administration, etc.). Nevertheless, many of the respondents considered CARL to be the most significant reform in the country because of its comprehensiveness. After the Corazon Aquino administration, the succeeding administrations did not change CARL. Instead, they tried to improve the program's implementation. Nevertheless, institutional constraints (e.g., changing priority areas, landed elites, landed political elites, legal loopholes, lack of budgetary requirements, land issues, the presence of militant groups in the provinces, and perceptions of ARBs on farming) have limited the outcomes and impacts of the agrarian reform efforts. Figure 8 shows the agrarian reform efforts from Corazon Aquino to Rodrigo Duterte, while Figure 9 illustrates the institutional limits and constraints encountered in these periods that hindered the achievement of the desired outcomes and impacts.

Corazon Aquino. The Corazon Aquino administration was compelled to pass a land reform law after the government killed 13 peasants at the Mendiola Bridge near Malacañang Palace during a huge peasant rally for agrarian reform authored by Kilusang Magbubukid ng Pilipinas (KPM) and its allies. However, landlords dominated the Congress (Borras, 2007). Also, cabinet members under Cory represented powerful businesses and political interests. The only supporter of redistributive reform within the cabinet was Solita Monsod, who was appointed head of the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) (Marin et al., 2019).

Such a political environment adversely affected the overall passage of CARL from the original House Bill 400 and how it was watered down from the House to the Senate deliberations. There were two bills that originated in the Lower House. These were Representative Bonifacio Gillego's HB 400 and Representative Romeo Guanzon and Hortencia Starke's HB 941 (Padilla, 1988). Representative Gillego's HB 400 was severely watered down even before the bill reached the floor (Putzel, 1992). The bill also raised the retention limit to 14 hectares and deleted its progressive features. Regarding Representative Guanzon's HB 941, it was described as the landlord's agrarian reform bill because it exempted private lands from land reform (Padilla, 1988).

In the Senate, there were two bills filed separately. The first version was from Senator Alvarez, which provided a retention limit of between seven and 24 hectares. Also, it exempted plantations from acquisition and distribution while requiring profit-sharing schemes for its workers. The second version was from Senator Agapito Aquino, which prohibited absentee landlordism and provided a retention limit of only three hectares (Padilla, 1988; Putzel, 1992).

On March 25, 1988, both the House and the Senate passed on second reading their final versions of CARL. The House had approved Representative Gillego's diluted HB 400, and the Senate had voted for Senator Alvarez's version. On April 21, 1988, the House passed the diluted HB 400 on the third and final reading. During this time, Representative Gillego withdrew from his own bill, saying that the landlords had already watered it down (Padilla, 1988; Putzel, 1992).

It is important to note that landowners engaged in an intense lobbying campaign all throughout Congressional deliberations. They argued that the liberal approach to agrarian reform was a discriminatory toward the rural property owners and would cause demise to the entire agriculture sector. The landowners also engaged with numerous small owners, trying to convince them that their interests were aligned (Putzel, 1992).

A bicameral conference was initiated to come up with a compromise bill that would satisfy both the House and the Senate. The issues discussed were about the timetable, scope and retention limit. On June 6, 1988, after weeks of bargaining and compromise, the committee approved the final agrarian reform measure. On June 10, 1988, CARL was signed into law (Padilla, 1988; Putzel, 1992).

The passage of RA 6657 was the result of a series of advocacy efforts started during the Marcos Sr. period. The grassroots-level movements, such as the Congress for People's Agrarian Reform (CPAR), heightened the demand for the CARP (Lanzona, 2019). A respondent agreed that the passage of CARL was a result of the civil society organization (CSO) movement. It was a significant symbol or manifestation of reform in the late 1980s to early 1990s (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

In contrast to previous policies that only covered rice and corn lands, CARL covered all types of lands, regardless of crops, for land acquisition and distribution (LAD). Aside from this, it included the provision of support services for ARBs (RA 6657, 1988). With this, the main objective of CARL was to achieve social justice (KII_005, personal communication, March 13, 2023). The Corazon Aquino administration envisioned equitable land ownership for small farmers (KII_011, personal communication, July 24, 2023).

CARL added the commercial farms of multinational corporations for acquisition and distribution. CARL was significant because of its inclusion of commercial farms (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023). However, Section 11 of CARL stated that the LAD of commercial farms was deferred for 10 years, from 1988 to 1998. Section 32 also mandated production-and-income sharing for workers on all commercial farms during the 10-year deferment period.

There were several policies implemented to facilitate CARP implementation. First, Proclamation No. 131 instituted the CARP as the major program of the government with a budget of PHP 50 billion for the period 1988-1998 (Proclamation No. 131, 1987). Second, Executive Order (EO) 229 provided the mechanisms for CARP's implementation (EO 229, 1987). Third, EO 129-A provided for the strengthening of DAR as the lead agency for CARP implementation. During the time of Marcos Sr., the function of DAR was to distribute land. Aside from land tenure improvement, there were two additional functions under the Aquino administration. These were the provisions for support services and agrarian justice (EO 129-A, 1987). Thus, DAR had to be strengthened because, at that time, they did not have the expertise and experience to provide support services for ARBs and to settle agrarian disputes.

Lastly, EO 405 vested LBP with the primary responsibility for land valuation (EO 405, 1990). In comparison to PD 27's valuation formula, the land valuation formula underwent changes during this time. The new formula took market value and zoning into account. Therefore, the valuation of rice and corn areas increased during the CARP implementation. This brought disappointment to landowners in rice and corn areas covered under PD 27 due to the low valuation given to them (Quizon, 2019).

Despite the promise to make the land of the tiller a reality, the Aquino administration yielded to the members of the political and economic elite dominating Congress and the Cabinet. Aquino's Cabinet appointees were chosen from the coalition that supported her presidential campaign. What made the selection of the Cabinet members intriguing was that they represented influential businesses with a more conservative view of agrarian reform. The only supporter among Cory's Cabinet members for agrarian reform was Solita Monsod, who was appointed as the NEDA Secretary (Marin et al., 2019).

On that note, a UPLB researcher (KII_003) expressed the same concern that the country's political actors have been landowners. Thus, she argued that Philippine agrarian reform has a political environment where there are uneven power dynamics. This situation exemplifies the symbiotic relationship between landlordship and political influence in the country. Meaning, the political and economic power of rich political landlords has allowed them to keep their lands across all administrations (KII_002, personal communication, February 14, 2023).

It was also observed that there was a lack of urgency in the Cory administration to appoint the Secretary of Agrarian Reform. It took Cory two months to appoint Agrarian Reform Secretary Heherson Alvarez, while the other Cabinet members were appointed two days after she assumed the office. Alvarez had no experience with agricultural or agrarian reform concerns, but he was a close friend of Ninoy Aquino when he was exiled to the United States (Putzel, 1992; Marin et al., 2019). This was contrary to people's anticipation of faster implementation of the program under the Aquino administration (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023).

In addition, the Aquino administration used CARL as a political commodity. Even though Aquino was wealthy, landed, and had a soft spot for the masses, politics became the main driver in the passage of CARL. The stock distribution option (SDO) in CARL was included to prevent the distribution of Hacienda Luisita (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

Aside from these concerns, the Aquino administration was unprepared to implement an extensive social justice program designed for farmers (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023). Aside from high administrative costs, Lanzona (2019) explained that CARL had forced the elites to circumvent the law. The following factors may contribute to these circumventions. First, CARP covered all land-related laws, not just those relating to agrarian reform. This might result in a variety of legal voids and conflicts involving everything from land valuation (like the Garchitorena scandal case) to land conversion (like the Marubeni case). Second, a comprehensive program implied that other government departments besides DAR would be involved in its implementation. More loopholes might be created as more organizations, such as the National Development Corporation (NDC) and Department of Agriculture (DA) become involved. Third, the implementation process might be difficult because different geographic areas and crops have their own unique agrarian structures. The range of support services would need to correspond with the diversity of crops, regions, and organizations. Thus, one could observe the distinct levels of dissatisfaction expressed by farmer groups in various locations (such as Sumilao/Mapalad and Calatagan) (Lanzona, 2019). A respondent agreed that CARP's loophole is to provide quality support services for the beneficiaries (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

On the part of the ARBs, there is a difference in attitudes and values among beneficiaries who received lands from the Marcos Sr. government as compared to the Aquino government. The perception of ARBs on land was for subsistence and survival during the Marcos Sr. administration. On the contrary, ARBs now perceive a lack of value for CARP-awarded lands (KII_008, personal communication, March 21, 2023).

In the end, the Aquino administration distributed almost two million ha of land to a million beneficiaries (Quizon, 2019). A respondent described it as a small accomplishment as far as land distribution was concerned from 1988 to 1999. She further explained that they had a project during the time of Secretary Garilao that helped DAR show the necessity of extending CARP. Unfortunately, at that time, Congress did not want to extend CARP and wanted to focus on provisions for support services instead (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

Fidel Ramos. The problem of elite domination of sectoral politics continued during the time of President Fidel Ramos. In the House, there were 29 members of the Committee on Agrarian Reform with substantial agricultural interests (Riedinger, 1994). Thus, Riedinger pointed out that the Philippine state is "ill-equipped to serve as a neutral arbiter of economic and political affairs" (1994, p.139).

In this type of political environment, Ramos used agrarian reform as the government's program for poverty alleviation. He implemented several agrarian reform-related policies. First, RA 7905 strengthened CARP's implementation (RA 7905, 1995). RA 7905, Section 3, specified the continuous application of leaseback arrangements, joint ventures, and other schemes to optimize the operating size for

agricultural production. Second, RA 8532 provided an extension of CARP with an additional P50B budget (RA 8532, 1998). Lastly, RA 7881 amended certain provisions of RA 6657, which exempted fishponds and prawn farms from CARP coverage (RA 7881, 1995).

It should be noted that it was during the Ramos administration that the 10-year commercial deferment period ended (Quizon, 2019). Commercial farm landowners opted for a 10-year deferment period rather than a physical land transfer to recover their expenses (KII_008, personal communication, March 2).

During this administration, the agrarian reform community (ARC) was a development program launched in 1993. An ARC was a barangay or cluster composed of farmers and farmer workers who were waiting for the agrarian reform implementation (Borras, 2007). The ARC development program contributed to the development of agrarian reform in the country for three reasons. First, the ARC strategy was a reason why the foreign donor community had serious and renewed interest in CARP. Under the Garilao administration at DAR (1992–1998), the department raised a billion dollars in foreign development assistance through ARC projects within four years. Second, the ARC strategy shielded CARP from anti-state actors, being careful not to antagonize foreign donors. Third, the ARC strategy can be viewed as a training group to develop skills related to rural development. However, rural social movement groups noted the exclusionary character of the ARC projects because there were only a few beneficiaries involved in such projects (Borras, 2007).

Like the previous administration, Ramos encountered institutional constraints in the program's implementation. Due to its targeted approach, the ARC strategy attracted numerous foreign funds, but it tended to favor those who could organize themselves (Marin et al., 2019). =There was a preference for foreign investors over local farmers (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

Another constraint has been the lack of a land management information system (LMIS), which is a root problem in land distribution. The country has an incomplete and inefficient land ownership database system (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023). For instance, there is conflicting content and coverage in the land databases of DAR, DENR, and the National Commission on Indigenous Peoples (NCIP). This is a major concern because of the numerous cases of land-related conflicts that remain unresolved (KII_005, personal communication, March 13, 2023). This is contrary to the cases of Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan, which have well-documented land ownership information and compensation systems in place for land acquisition, making the process smoother and more efficient compared to the Philippines (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

In connection with this, most of the lands distributed during Ramos administration were government-owned lands (Marin et al., 2019). This is because of the strong resistance from landlords, which has been a major constraint to the implementation of agrarian reform efforts (Galang, 2020). There have been delays in the notice of acquisition precisely because the politicians are also the owners of the big landholdings (KII_012, personal communication, July 26, 2023).

There have also been concerns about land conversion. In the period 1992 to 1997, DAR received 1,027 requests for land use conversion involving 12,541 hectares, of which 875 were granted. Quizon (2019) noted that most of these conversions were illegal due to the absence of an effective law on land use.

On that note, a former NGO legal officer (KII_001) believed that there was an evolution of early agrarian reform laws towards a more distributive and comprehensive approach over time. The caveat, however, was the lack of implementation. Another respondent agreed that the concept of CARP is good, but the problem is implementation (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

At the end of the administration, DAR had distributed 350,000 hectares by the end of the year, exceeding its target of 400,000 to 420,000 ha. It should be noted that two-thirds of this total was government-owned land. The complicated process of redistributing private lands continued to be a major concern during this period (Riedinger, 1994). Marin et al. agreed that the implementation of Ramos' agrarian reform had "increased momentum and modest success" (2019, p. 130) because millions of lands were distributed to two million beneficiaries. Unfortunately, critics note that most of the lands distributed were less contentious in ownership and mode of acquisition (Marin et al., 2019).

Joseph Estrada. Joseph Estrada was ousted in 2001 and was consequently found guilty of plunder. He served for only two years, from 1998 to 2000. During his time, agrarian reform became the government's program for poverty alleviation. This was in line with his populist slogan, "*Erap para sa mahirap*" (Erap for the poor), which helped him win the May 1998 elections (Batalla, 2016).

In terms of the political and economic environment, DAR continued to rely on foreign funding (Marin et al., 2019). It was also during the time of Estrada that DAR promoted agribusiness partnerships toward increased productivity and incomes (Marin et al., 2019). The goal was to transform ARBs into farmer-entrepreneurs. A UPLB researcher (KII_003) confirmed the commercial orientation of agriculture in the country. Another respondent noted the preference of ARBs over commercial crops because of their high profits (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

In line with this, DAR expanded the ARC strategy to promote AVAs and economic enterprises through the passage of DAR AO 9 of 1998 (Rules and Regulations on the Acquisition, Valuation, Compensation, and Distribution of Deferred Commercial Farms). DAR AO 02 of 1999 (Rules and Regulations Governing Joint Economic Enterprises in Agrarian Reform Areas) repealed AO 9 of 1998. From July 1998 to December 2000, DAR reported a total of 380 new ARCs established, involving 73,067 ARBs and 178,291 ha of land distributed. DAR organized 638 farmer cooperatives and associations with a total of 44,056 registered ARB members (Marin et al., 2019).

ARBs have three roles in agribusiness venture arrangement (AVA). First, ARBs have a role as landowners due to the agrarian reform program. Second, ARBs have a role as farmworkers due to investors. Lastly, ARBs have a role as cooperative members. With these roles, ARBs have three sources of income in AVA: 1) rental fees as landowners; 2) salaries earned as farmworkers; and 3) dividends as cooperative members (KII_009, personal communication, May 26, 2023).

However, DAR's dwindling funds and resources affected the provision of support services (Marin et al., 2019). Complementary reinforcing mechanisms are crucial for the success of agrarian reform, particularly in the context of AVA. Mechanisms should include support services, rural infrastructure, fair trade practices, and negotiating powers in rural markets and the entire value chain. However, there is the dominance of agribusiness in the country's economy at the expense of social considerations (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

Figure 8
Agrarian Reform (Policy Path)

Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents)

Figure 8 (continued)
Agrarian Reform (Policy Path)

Aside from the constraints in AVA implementation, there are concerns about the overall agrarian reform efforts. The resistance from big landlords continued during this period. While DAR continued with land distribution on both public and private lands, landlords have used delaying tactics to completely evade the distribution of their lands (Marin et al., 2019). A UPLB researcher (KII_004) agreed on the political and legal constraints (i.e., the ability of private landowners to contest government actions) on agrarian reform.

Also, capitalist structures and values have undermined sociocultural development, which is a pillar of agriculture. She argued that Filipinos go abroad and sell their land. This is because they do not feel that there is dignity in farming (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

In connection with this, even though all administrations recognize agriculture's importance as the country's economic foundation, many interventions and development-related push factors are concentrated in other sectors (service and manufacturing) rather than agriculture (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

Gloria Macapagal Arroyo. Estrada was impeached through People Power 2 because of corruption and economic mismanagement. This led to the government's takeover by Vice President Gloria Macapagal Arroyo. Arroyo's administration began in 2001 and ended in 2010 (Batalla, 2016). During this period, Arroyo implemented agrarian reform as a government program to alleviate poverty. The Medium-Term PDP 2001-2004 acknowledged that inequitable land distribution has been one of the biggest factors in poverty and social unrest (NEDA, 2001).

On that note, Arroyo and her allies in Congress passed RA 9700, or the Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Program Extension with Reforms (CARPER) bill. It provided additional funding of PHP 150 billion from 2009 to 2014 (Elvinia, 2011; Carranza, 2016). The five-year period was deemed sufficient to complete LAD. In this case, the Arroyo administration expressed its commitment to the full implementation of the land redistribution within a decade and at the same time strengthened the support services for the beneficiaries (NEDA, 2001).

Tadem (2015) described CARPER as the by-product of pro- and anti-agrarian reform blocs in Congress. It was the result of pro-agrarian reform because it continued provisions in favor of ARBs. Some of these provisions included the removal of the stock distribution option, the reinstatement of compulsory acquisition and voluntary offers-of-sale as the main redistribution modes, and the recognition of women as beneficiaries. Tadem (2015) clarified that the inclusion of these provisions was the result of the relentless struggle of peasant and farmer groups to assert their rights.

Unfortunately, landowner lobbyists inserted provisions in CARPER that can be considered legal loopholes. The anti-agrarian reform bloc inserted a "killer amendment" that allowed landowners to determine who would become beneficiaries under CARP coverage. Other than this, one can notice the expanding list of exempted lands (Tadem, 2015). This explained why a UPLB researcher (KII_003) argued that while there were revisions to CARP, not all ideas from the discussions with farmers were included. In this case, she highlighted the influence of political dynasties and landowners in Congress on agrarian reform policies like CARPER.

Like Ramos and Erap, the Arroyo administration used the ARC approach as a strategy for integrated delivery of various support services from the government, including education and training, health, and credit (NEDA, 2001). The administration repealed DAR AO 2 of 1999 with the passage of DAR AO 9 of 2006 (Revised Rules and Regulations Governing Agribusiness Venture Arrangements in Agrarian Reform Areas). It also passed DAR AO 2 of 2008 to protect ARBs involved in lease agreements (Guidelines Governing Lease of Lands under Agribusiness Venture Arrangement [AVA] in Agrarian Reform Areas and the Determination of Lease Rental Thereof). DAR AO 2 of 2008 defined the lease rental formula, which was not present in previous AOs in AVAs. In this case, the commercial orientation of Philippine agriculture (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

Despite the amendments to the AVA guidelines, there have been constraints in their implementation. There has been non-adherence to the lease rental formula in DAR AO 2 of 2008 (KII_009, personal communication, May 26, 2023). Another respondent argued that there has been weak monitoring and evaluation of AVAs. The lack of manpower, corruption, and appropriate tools are contributing factors to the failure of AVA monitoring and evaluation (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

At the end of the Arroyo administration, there were shortcomings in achieving targeted farm income and productivity in CARP (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023). In terms of the total LAD accomplishment, DAR distributed 808,134 hectares or 21%. It should be noted that 69% of these were private lands; thus, this contributed to the slow pace of land distribution. Also, five DAR secretaries held office during the 10 years of the Arroyo administration, which had an impact on the program due to the frequent changes in DAR leadership (Quizon, 2019).

Thus, while the country acknowledges the importance of agriculture as the economic backbone, it is ironic that most of the interventions can be found in sectors like service and manufacturing (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

Benigno Aquino III. Like the previous administrations, agrarian reform was one of the programs of the Aquino administration aimed at eradicating poverty. CARP was viewed as a social justice and poverty alleviation program because it involved not only land distribution but also the provision of support services to improve the socio-economic status of ARBs (Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018).

Thus, in the Philippine Development Plan 2011-2016, the Aquino administration expressed its objectives to fast-track the implementation of agrarian reform, specifically the distribution of individual land titles, to provide security of tenure and access to finance for ARBs. PDP 2011-2016 also pointed out the goal of transforming ARBs into viable entrepreneurs. To do so, there was a need to expand the support services and technical assistance for beneficiaries (NEDA, 2014).

To achieve this, the administration implemented the Agrarian Reform Community Connectivity and Economic Support Services (ARCESS) program. ARCESS was conceptualized from 2010 to 2011 and rolled out in 2012 (Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018; Marin et al., 2019). It aimed to help beneficiaries improve their farm productivity by involving them in agri-based enterprises. ARCESS capacitated agrarian reform beneficiary organizations (ARBOs) in handling business activities related to farm production, postharvest, processing, and marketing (Marin

et al., 2019). Aside from ARCESS, the administration provided microfinance and credit assistance to ARBOs. 5464 ARBOs received a total of PHP8.338 billion in microfinance and credit assistance.

In connection with this, the administration implemented the Agrarian Production Credit Program (APCP). APCP is a credit facility designed to meet the financing needs of ARBOs and their members. The program has two major objectives: 1) to increase ARBOs and ARBs' access to credit and 2) to improve their capacities (Agrarian Production Credit Program, 2021). LBP, DA, and DAR initially implemented the program. Eventually, the program incorporated the DENR and the Agricultural Credit Policy Council (ACPC). LBP provides for APCP's lending resources using its internal funds, which are also used as guarantees against loan default (Llanto et al., 2016).

Aside from these, DAR developed a web-based information system in 2011. Specifically, it created the DAR-Legal Information System (LIS), or the electronic legal library. LIS allowed DAR officials, agrarian reform advocates, and other stakeholders to access agrarian reform-related cases without having to call or travel to a DAR office to follow up on a case. A Legal Case Monitoring System (LCMS) was utilized in 2012 to manage the database of agrarian cases. The system helped DAR officials monitor pending cases in the department as well as in other courts (Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018; Marin et al., 2019).

There are institutional constraints on Aquino's agrarian reform efforts. One of these was the illegal land conversion that continued due to the lack of an effective law on land use. From 2010 to 2015, DAR received 142 applications for land use conversion covering 3,892 hectares, of which 101 were approved. Like the Ramos administration, the Aquino administration saw a significant amount of illegal land conversion. Quizon (2019) attributed these rampant illegal conversions to the absence of an effective land use law. The National Land Use Act has been pending in Congress since the 1990s (Quizon, 2019).

Another constraint was that there has been slow LAD performance. In the assessment report of Villamejor-Mendoza et al. (2018), the fact that the LAD process is not the sole work of DAR and that there are other government agencies involved contributed to the slow LAD performance of the Aquino administration (Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018). Quizon (2019) explained that there are five government agencies involved in the LAD process. These are the DAR, DENR, the Land Registration Authority (LRA), the Registry of Deeds (ROD), and the LBP. Each of them has its role in the LAD process. DAR is the primary implementing agency of the LAD. DENR and LRA provide administrative support in terms of land information, land surveys, and land registration. LBP determines the land valuation, pays landowners, and offers financing to ARBs for the acquisition of CARP lands. Thus, certificate of land ownership award (CLOA) are mortgaged to LBP, and mortgages are canceled after the full payment of an ARB (Quizon, 2019). From this, one can infer that the multiplicity of implementing agencies enabled bureaucratic delays in ensuring due process.

Many authors agreed that the performance of the Aquino administration in LAD was quite slow (Tadem, 2015; Carranza, 2016; Villamejor-Mendoza et al., 2018; Quizon, 2019). The Aquino administration promised to distribute 1.2 million ha, but by December 2015, it had only distributed 534,812 hectares, or less than half the goal (Quizon, 2019).

Figure 9
Agrarian Reform (Institutional Constraints)

Figure 9 (continued)
Agrarian Reform (Institutional Constraints)

Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents) Source. (Author's illustration based on the KII themes and primary and secondary documents)

Rodrigo Duterte. Bello (2019) elucidated that the failure of the EDSA liberal democratic regime to deliver the political and economic reforms that it had promised paved the way for Duterte's rise into power. There was a disappointing record on agrarian reform in 2014, wherein 700,000 hectares of private land remained undistributed. Thus, by the 2016 election, there was a gap between the EDSA Republic's promise of wealth distribution and the reality of massive poverty. In addition, the Aquino administration was widely seen as having inept governance. As a result, Duterte gained approval from all classes as the tough guy with an authoritarian approach, especially from the middle-class base. Such an image of Duterte was developed since he was the mayor of Davao for 30 years.

During the Duterte administration, agrarian reform became an instrument for poverty alleviation. In its 10-point socioeconomic agenda, land reform was one of the priorities of the administration. Specifically, the agenda states, "Ensure security of land tenure to encourage investments and address bottlenecks among land management and titling agencies" (Department of Finance, 2023, para. 14). In the same way, a DAR regional official (KII_011) expressed that the government envisioned equitable land ownership for the small and marginalized farmers. Nevertheless, Bello (2019) argued that there was no new legislation to push forward the agrarian reform. This was because one of Duterte's most well-known House of Representatives supporters was from the Visayan bloc of landowners. He further explained that Duterte's economic team would only continue the neoliberal policies of the Aquino administration and focused to craft a new tax reform to address the rise of the inflation rate in 2018.

In terms of the political and economic environment, the Presidential Agrarian Reform Council (PARC) was on hiatus from 2006 to 2016, and ARBs continued to engage in illegal lease transactions due to a lack of sufficient support services (Pangulayan, 2019). In connection with this, PARC should be the one to formulate the LAD master plan. However, it did not materialize because PARC had been inactive for 10 years (2006-2016) when the CARPER deadline took effect. This led to a delay in distributing private agricultural lands, which were the most challenging type of land to implement under CARP due to the resistance of landowners.

Aside from this, there was a major concern of the Duterte administration about the implementation of CARP, which was merely distributing collective certificates of land ownership awards (CCLOA) rather than individual titles. In the 2017-2022 PDP, it explained how investor confidence in lands awarded under CARP has been eroded because of incomplete land ownership transfers to ARBs from collective to individual titles (NEDA, 2023).

To address these concerns, Duterte reactivated PARC and signed an order ordering all government agencies to transfer all government-owned farmlands to the DAR and put them under CARP coverage for distribution to landless farmers following Executive Order (EO) 75 of 2019. EO 75 included properties of state universities and properties (EO 75, 2019). EO 75 extended coverage to government-owned lands for distribution (KII_009, personal communication, May 26, 2023). Another DAR official explained that there is a need to transfer unused government-owned lands to DAR. This is because the government owns agriculturally productive lands that are not being farmed (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023). Thus, EO 75 aimed for the government's acquisition of idle and abandoned lands for agrarian reform.

In line with Duterte's marching order, DAR issued AO 2 of 2019, which provided guidelines to cover the parcelization of all landholdings with CCLOAs given to farmer's cooperatives, farmers' associations, organized groups of ARBs, or several ARBs not organized. Aside from the issuance of AO 2 of 2019, DAR created the Agrarian Reform Title Stabilization (ARTS) to facilitate the parcelization process (Galang, 2020).

The passage of EO 75 of 2019 and DAR AO 2 of 2019 aimed to strengthen the capacity of DAR to parcelize the landholdings awarded to ARBs under a collective and unsubdivided form of ownership. DAR strengthened the process [of distributing lands] by taking actions before receiving the Date of Transfer. Also, EO 75, DAR, and the Department of Justice coordinate in advancing land distribution (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023).

The PARC revoked SDO plans under CARL. PARC also revoked some unfair AVA contracts. Additionally, 47,377 land titles covering 71,198.35 hectares of agricultural land were distributed to over 46,000 ARBs, with more than half of the 24,605 of the 46,338 farmer-beneficiaries coming from Central Luzon, 11,859 from CALABARZON, and 9,874 from MIMAROPA receiving 20,982.96, 21,119.94, and 29,095.45 hectares, respectively. Through EO 75, the administration distributed at least 300,000 ha of unused government-owned lands to farmers, including 8,000 ha from the Yulo King Ranch in Busuanga, Coron, Palawan; 5,000 in the Davao Penal Colony in Davao del Norte; and 110 in the Aurora State College of Technology in Baler, Aurora (Gallardo, 2019). DAR Secretary Estrella Jr. noted that the scope of EPs, CLOAs, and registrations from 1972 to June 2022 covered 5,463,827 hectares, but there are many areas under EO 75 pending distribution (Carias, 2022).

The Duterte government encountered the same institutional constraints in the implementation of its agrarian reform efforts. One of these is the challenge of accessing military camp lands to be covered for agrarian reform. It is important to take note that there are areas suitable for agriculture within a military camp. DAR tried to talk to a representative from the military camp, but they did not respond (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023).

Another constraint is the opposition of the rich landowners. DAR provincial officers face various opponents who are against land distribution, including rich landowners. Also, private landowners filed cases against DAR officers for doing their jobs (KII_006, personal communication, March 13, 2023). In response, a DAR regional official (KII_011) agreed that the stagnation of agrarian reform efforts is due to landowner resistance. Nevertheless, the government cannot just freely give the land because it is private property, and they must go through the landowners before transferring the land (KII_004, personal communication, March 10, 2023).

In addition, DAR cannot award land titles to ARBs because of the New People's Army (NPA)'s interference in Negros (KII_005, personal communication, March 13, 2023). From this, one can infer that the presence of the NPA is a challenge to implementation in the second generation.

In terms of attitudes and values among ARBs, capitalist structures and values have undermined sociocultural development, which is a pillar in agriculture. To put it bluntly, the new generation of farmers has left farming because they view farming as poverty (KII_003, personal communication, February 27, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Philippine agrarian reform is highly politicized for three reasons. First, political motivations have become a major driver in shaping the country's agrarian reform efforts. This can be exemplified in the first and second generations. While there is a policy intent to improve the lives of farmers, politics has become a deterrent to achieving this goal. Second, the country's agrarian reform has a highly political environment where there are unequal power dynamics between farmers and landowners. While peasants and farmers have received political support from the CSOs, one can observe the strong influence of landowners, specifically those who are also political actors. The strong resistance of landowners to land distribution has the net effect of dragging out CARP implementation. Lastly, the landed political elites have been dominating Congress. It is important to note that there is a symbiotic and mutual power dynamic between landownership and political influence. This means that the political and economic power of rich landlords allows them to keep their land and protect their property. Most importantly, they can determine what should be regulated, when, how, why, and by whom.

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